

The Coupling Constants Series and The Electron – 8 Theory

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April 16, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the coupling constants series and in particular using the prime critical line, we can reach wonderful representation of spin and correlate the majestic (3) to the electron. By doing so describe the process of propagation of bosons from fermion clusters and more coherent and vivid way than any other theory.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \rightarrow \frac{3^2}{128} \quad (1.15)$$

Recall that arbitrary variations vanish in pairs of even numbers. That axiom in our framework related to fermions and allowed us to make a transformation regarding the strong interaction:

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1) \quad (1.16)$$

So we can vary (2) to prove that the majestic three is indeed an electron and solidify our theory and its validity:

$$\frac{3^2}{128} = \frac{8 + (1)}{128} \quad (1.17)$$

Even amount of variations taken to vanish so the final form of equation (2) is exactly like equation (1.14) and so we verify that it is in fact the electron:

$$\frac{8 + (1)}{128} \rightarrow \frac{(1)}{128} = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \quad (1.18)$$

Perfect clusters of variations are destabilized by the electron, which blends in the cluster, and the end result is the net curvature on the manifold, which is the photon, in that case, $N_V = (+5)$

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)